

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

THE ROLE OF 20-HETE IN LUNG CANCERS¹Tahreem Asim, ²Dr Yusra Iqbal, ³Dr Ambreen Ayesha¹DHQ Hospital Gujranwala, ²UHS, Lahore, ³WMO, THQ, Pattoki, Kasur.

Article Received: April 2019

Accepted: May 2019

Published: June 2019

Abstract:

The ω -hydroxylation of AA produces significant 20-hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid "20-HETE" levels among different tissues. This research aims to evaluate the role of 20-HETE in lung cancers in both pathophysiological and physiological states. Although, the role of 20-HETE is not clear in liver but it represents liver CYP-dependent AA metabolism (50% – 75%) along with its association to liver cirrhotic ascites. Moreover, 20-HETE also carries mitogenic and angiogenic characteristics which help the promotion of tumor. Several inducers and inhibitors of 20-HETE synthesis as well as 20-HETE antagonists and analogues are potent treatment options for various diseases. Lung Cancer causes majority of deaths all over the world which indicates for the availability of better treatment options. Various therapeutic targets have been set for provision of suitable treatment options such as eicosanoid metabolism pathway which involves various lipid generations as these lipids are not regulated in different cancers and inhibition of these lipids in order to reduce the onset of lung cancer. However, no research work is available about the involvement of enzymes in eicosanoid metabolism correlated with lung cancer. The ω -hydroxylation of AA produces significant 20-hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid "20-HETE" levels among different tissues. This research aims to evaluate the role of 20-HETE in lung cancers in both pathophysiological and physiological states. Although, the role of 20-HETE is not clear in liver but it represents liver CYP-dependent AA metabolism (50% – 75%) along with its association to liver cirrhotic ascites. Moreover, 20-HETE also carries mitogenic and angiogenic characteristics which help the promotion of tumor. Several inducers and inhibitors of 20-HETE synthesis as well as 20-HETE antagonists and analogues are potent treatment options for various diseases.

Keywords: 20-HETE (20-hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid), Liver, Cancer, Tumor, Diagnosis, Tissue, Cirrhotic, Ischemia and Treatment.

Corresponding author:**Tahreem Asim,**

DHQ Hospital Gujranwala.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Tahreem Asim et al., **The Role Of 20-Hete In Lung Cancers.**, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci.*, 2019; 06(06).

INTRODUCTION:

Notably, eicosanoids exert action through eicosanoid receptors which are specified in nature along with PPAR receptors (non-specific receptors). 20-HETE receptor identification will help in the increased understanding of clinical implications and molecular mechanisms of 20-HETE in various organs. This research aims to evaluate the role of 20-HETE in lung cancers in both pathophysiological and physiological states [1]. More than One billion deaths are attributed to lung cancer every year all over the world [2, 3]. An advanced disease stage is the basic reason of this high mortality rate. Delayed diagnosis prevents the successful surgical resection. Such cases are approached with different available treatment modalities such as radiation and chemotherapy which is less productive in comparison to the localized disease resection [4, 5]. The survival rate is restricted to five years among 18% patients due to aggressive disease nature which clearly requires more precise and effective treatment modality [5]. For better treatment options we need to target those processes which affect the progression of tumor. Primarily, tumor cells depend on the paracrine and autocrine release which promotes the growth of the tumor and it also changes the response of TME (Tumor Microenvironment). As a result, the TME cells (fibroblasts, macrophages and endothelial cells) can secrete those factors which affect the tumor cell response and this process also regulates cancer cell proliferation, neovascularization, metastasis and migration [6]. Eicosanoids are the major group which alters the process of secreted factors. TME cells or tumor cells produce these molecules which affects the processes of angiogenesis, inflammation and tumor dissemination [7].

Eicosanoid metabolites come from arachidonic acid metabolism by lipoxygenase (LOX), cyclooxygenase (COX) and cytochrome P monooxygenase. Every branch produces specific eicosanoid metabolites which have different biological outcomes. COX-driven products start with prostaglandin endoperoxide prostaglandin H2 (PGH2) production by COX – I or II. Careful prostaglandin synthases convert it into proteinoids which include prostaglandin D2 (PGD2), thromboxane (TXA2), prostaglandin F2 (PGF2 α), prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) and prostaglandin I2 (PGI2). Hydro eicosatetraenoic acids (HETEs), lipoxins and leukotrienes are the outcomes of LOX pathway metabolized arachidonic acid. Cytochrome P monooxygenases metabolizes arachidonic acid in to 20 HETE or epoxy eicosatrienoic acids (EETs) [7]. Terminal hydroxylation of AA is established as a reaction known as ω -hydroxylation in which AA

converts in to 20-HETE through CYP4F enzymes and CYP4A enzymes [5 – 7].

COX has an important role to play in the 20-HETE metabolism which gives a range of different organ activities [8]. COX metabolizes 20-HETE into vasoconstrictor prostaglandin H2 (20-OH PGH2) hydroxyl analogue that is transformed by isomerases in to diuretic/ vasodilator metabolites (20-OH PGI2, 20-OH PGE2) and antidiuretic/ vasoconstrictor metabolites (20-OH PGF2 α , 20-OH Thromboxane A2) [8 – 10]. Various inhibitors for 20-HETE synthesis have also been used in the past which includes N-methylsulfonyl-12, 17-octadecynoic acid (17-ODYA), dibromododec-11-enoic acid (DBDD), 12-dibromododec-11-enamide (DDMS) etc. [5, 6, 11 – 15]. Evidence is also available about the use of nonselective inhibitors of AA metabolism such as Cobalt (II) chloride (CoCl2) and 1-Aminobenzotriazole (ABT) [16, 17]. Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha (PPAR α) agonists (clofibrate and fenofibrate) or gene therapy are used for the 20-HETE formation upregulation along with 20- hydroxyeicosa-5(Z), 20-HETE mimetics, 14(Z)-dienoic acid and N-[20-hydroxyeicosa- 5(Z),14(Z)-dienoyl glycine [18, 19].

PATIENTS & METHODS:

This research was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from October 2017 to December 2018 on a total of 395 patients who presented a history of smoking. Patients were enrolled after informed consent and permission of hospital's ethical review committee. They were also explained about the research protocols.

RESULTS:

In the total research sample 55.2% patients of lung cancer were at distant stage of the disease. About 37% patients were predominately adenocarcinoma as observed through histology. Lung cancer and squamous cell carcinoma were respectively diagnosed in 27.6% and 27.9%. Lung cancer treatment primarily consisted of radiation, chemotherapy and surgical resection. Majority of the patients did not receive single treatment modality such as surgical resection which is limited to regional and local stage of the disease. Patients who underwent (21.3%) combination of radiation and chemotherapy as common treatment modalities. About 22% patients did not receive any of the treatment modality. Information was not available about 15% patients for one or more than treatment variables. Improved outcomes of surgical resection were reported in females. Increased mortality rate was also due to increased consumption of cigarette.

Detailed outcomes about clinical and demographic profile of the patients are available in Table – I and

outcomes of treatment combination variables are given in Table – II.

Table – I: Clinical and Demographic Profile

Characteristic		Number	Percentage
Gender	Male	219	55.4
	Female	176	44.6
Vital Status	Died	333	84.3
	Alive	62	15.7
Self-Reported COPD	Absent	330	83.5
	Present	64	16.2
	Missing	1	0.3
Mean Value	Cigarettes (Days)	19.2	13.7
	Missing	5	1.3
	Mean age at diagnosis (Years)	60.4	8.8
Cancer Stage	Localized	56	14.2
	Regional	113	28.6
	Distant	218	55.2
	Missing	8	2
Histology	Adenocarcinoma	146	37
	NSCLC NOS	109	27.6
	NSCLC Other	32	8.1
	Squamous cell carcinoma	110	27.9
Surgical Resection	Absent	296	74.9
	Present	74	18.7
	Missing	25	6.3
Chemotherapy	Absent	202	51.1
	Present	169	42.8
	Missing	24	6.1
Radiation	Absent	208	52.7
	Present	149	37.8
	Missing	38	9.6

Table – II: Treatment Combination Variables

Treatment Combination	Number	Percentage
No Treatment	87	22.00
Surgical Resection Only	47	11.90
Only Chemotherapy	49	12.40
Only Radiation	45	11.40
Surgical Resection + Chemotherapy	11	2.80
Surgical resection + Radiation	6	1.50
Chemotherapy + Radiation	84	21.30
Surgical Resection + Rhemotherapy + Radiation	8	2.00
More than One Treatment Variables	58	14.70

DISCUSSION:

It is interesting to note that 50% to 75% of CYP-dependent AA metabolites form in the liver by liver microsomes (19-HETE & 20-HETE); whereas, 20-HETE reportedly forms metabolite [20]. AA ω -hydroxylation in the liver of human is catalyzed by CYP4F3, CYP4F2 and CYP4A11 [21]. Most hepatic 20-HETE are formed through CYP4F2 which is a liver-specific CYP4F3 splice variant [22]. Increased 20-HETE synthesis is induced by human hepatocyte-like Hepa RG, CYP4F3B and hepatoma cell line [23]. Moreover, statins recruited PXR for the induction of CYP4F3B [24]. Isoniazid lowers the formation and expression of 20-HETE and CYP4A in liver [25]. The information about the role of 20-HETE in liver is not well established; however, it regulates metabolic activity of the liver and hemodynamics [26]. 20-HETE can be important for functions like lipid homeostasis and for the control of metabolism and fat-dependent energy. It is also important for the inflammatory diseases as it acts like inflammatory mediators [27]. 20-HETE is COX dependent, weak, portal circulation vasoconstrictor and supposedly involved in the portal hypertension pathophysiology. It is also involved in the liver related disease abnormalities specially in the cirrhotic cases. Presently, 20-HETE has also demonstrated counter regulatory effect in the liver on endogenous peroxygenases. Therefore, EETs and 20-HETE tuning, degradation and formation provide treatment benefits if there are opposite effects for various other diseases. Level of 20-HETE is increased

in the urine samples of cirrhotic patients having ascites than cirrhotic patients without ascites; it is also more than the excretion rates of normal patients [28]. Hepatic cirrhosis patients have higher production of 20-HETE in preglomerular microcirculation which results in renal vasculature constriction, reduced renal blood flow and depressed renal hemodynamics.

20-HETE induces angiogenic and mitogenic responses in vivo and vitro. It is a mitogen for the smooth cells of the muscle. 20-HETE promotes tumor metastasis and angiogenesis in human lungs; it also promotes proliferation and mitogenicity in renal epithelial cells [29]. In prostate cancer and benign prostatic hypertrophy patients, 20-HETE urinary concentrations are higher than normal patients which were reduced by removing prostate gland. Vanella presented that ellagic acid mediates a pathway for its inherited chemotherapeutic feature which is other than its pro-differentiation and anti-proliferative features, it all occurs by a mechanism which involves reduced 20-HETE synthesis in the cells of prostate cancer [30]. Stabilized CYP4Z1 expression in T47D human breast cancer cells may also lead to increased 20-HETE contents; whereas, HET0016 inhibits tumor-induced angiogenesis with related changes in the 20-HETE's intracellular levels [31]. Similarly, the samples taken from breast, thyroid, ovarian and colon cancer also revealed that CYP4A/4F genes are increased in the samples of cancer than normal subjects [32].

CONCLUSION:

Various member of CYP ω -hydroxylase enzymes demonstrate 20-HETE formation; however, it predominantly differs in different organs and even differs in males and females. Its role is negative in vasculature and heart. Levels of 20-HETE are increased in the liver pathophysiological disease with cirrhotic ascites state. With 20-HETE's vasoconstrictor effect it appears as tumor suppressor. Studies prove that formation of tumor is promoted by 20-HETE by its mitogenesis and angiogenesis features. More research work will even elaborate and establish the role of 20-HETE for liver cancers and associated disorders. Moreover, 20-HETE also carries mitogenic and angiogenic characteristics which help the promotion of tumor. Several inducers and inhibitors of 20-HETE synthesis as well as 20-HETE antagonists and analogues are potent treatment options for various diseases.

REFERENCES:

- Hada, M., Edin, M. L., Hartge, P., Lih, F. B., Wentzensen, N., Zeldin, D. C., & Trabert, B. (2019). Prediagnostic Serum Levels of Fatty Acid Metabolites and Risk of Ovarian Cancer in the Prostate, Lung, Colorectal, and Ovarian (PLCO) Cancer Screening Trial. *Cancer Epidemiology and Prevention Biomarkers*, 28(1), 189-197.
- Lukic, A., Wahlund, C. J., Gómez, C., Brodin, D., Samuelsson, B., Wheelock, C. E., ... & Rådmark, O. (2019). Exosomes and cells from lung cancer pleural exudates transform LTC₄ to LTD₄, promoting cell migration and survival via CysLT₁. *Cancer letters*, 444, 1-8.
- Pakiet, A., Kobiela, J., Stepnowski, P., Sledzinski, T., & Mika, A. (2019). Changes in lipids composition and metabolism in colorectal cancer: a review. *Lipids in health and disease*, 18(1), 29.
- Marji, J.S.; Wang, M.H.; Laniado-Schwartzman, M. Cytochrome P-450 4a isoform expression and 20-HETE synthesis in renal preglomerular arteries. *Am. J. Physiol. Renal Physiol.* 2002, 283, 60–67.
- Wang, M.H.; Guan, H.; Nguyen, X.; Zand, B.A.; Nasjletti, A.; Laniado-Schwartzman, M. Contribution of cytochrome P-450 4a1 and 4a2 to vascular 20-hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid synthesis in rat kidneys. *Am. J. Physiol.* 1999, 276, 246–253.
- Zhao, X.; Imig, J.D. Kidney cyP450 enzymes: Biological actions beyond drug metabolism. *Curr. Drug Metab.* 2003, 4, 73-84.
- Ward, N.C.; Tsai, I.J.; Barden, A.; van Bockxmeer, F.M.; Puddey, I.B.; Hodgson, J.M.; Croft, K.D. A single nucleotide polymorphism in the cyp4f2 but not cyp4a11 gene is associated with increased 20-HETE excretion and blood pressure. *Hypertension* 2008, 51, 1393–1398.
- Harder, D.R.; Campbell, W.B.; Roman, R.J. Role of cytochrome P-450 enzymes and metabolites of arachidonic acid in the control of vascular tone. *J. Vasc. Res.* 1995, 32, 79–92.
- Wang, J.S.; Zhang, F.; Jiang, M.; Wang, M.H.; Zand, B.A.; Abraham, N.G.; Nasjletti, A.; Laniado-Schwartzman, M. Transfection and functional expression of CYP4A1 and CYP4A2 using bicistronic vectors in vascular cells and tissues. *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.* 2004, 311, 913–920.
- Kaide, J.; Wang, M.H.; Wang, J.S.; Zhang, F.; Gopal, V.R.; Falck, J.R.; Nasjletti, A.; Laniado-Schwartzman, M. Transfection of CYP4A1 cDNA increases vascular reactivity in renal interlobar arteries. *Am. J. Physiol. Renal Physiol.* 2003, 284, 51–56.
- Fan, F.; Ge, Y.; Lv, W.; Elliott, M.R.; Muroya, Y.; Hirata, T.; Booz, G.W.; Roman, R.J. Molecular mechanisms and cell signaling of 20-hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid in vascular pathophysiology. *Front Biosci.* 2016, 21, 736 1427–1463.
- McGiff, J.C.; Quilley, J. 20-HETE and the kidney: Resolution of old problems and new beginnings. *Am. J. Physiol.* 1999, 277, 607–623.
- Carroll, M.A.; McGiff, J.C. A new class of lipid mediators: Cytochrome P450 arachidonate metabolites. *Thorax* 2000, 55 (Suppl 2), 13–16.
- Oyekan, A.O.; McGiff, J.C. Functional response of the rat kidney to inhibition of nitric oxide synthesis: Role of cytochrome P450-derived arachidonate metabolites. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* 1998, 125, 1065–1073.
- Askari, B.; Bell-Quilley, C.P.; Fulton, D.; Quilley, J.; McGiff, J.C. Analysis of eicosanoid mediation of the renal functional effects of hyperchloremia. *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.* 1997, 282, 101–107.
- Xu, F.; Straub, W.O.; Pak, W.; Su, P.; Maier, K.G.; Yu, M.; Roman, R.J.; Ortiz De Montellano, P.R.; Kroetz, D.L. Antihypertensive effect of mechanism-based inhibition of renal arachidonic acid omega-hydroxylase activity. *Am. J. Physiol. Regul. Integr. Comp. Physiol.* 2002, 283, 710–720.
- Williams, J.M.; Murphy, S.; Burke, M.; Roman, R.J. 20-hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid: A new target for the treatment of hypertension. *J. Cardiovasc. Pharmacol.* 2010, 56, 336–344.
- Tunctan, B.; Korkmaz, B.; Buharalioglu, C.K.; Firat, S.S.; Anjaiah, S.; Falck, J.; Roman, R.J.;

- Malik, K.U. A 20-hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid agonist, n-[20-hydroxyeicosa-5(z),14(z)-dienoylglycine, opposes the fall in blood pressure and vascular reactivity in endotoxin-treated rats. *Shock* 2008, 30, 329–335.
19. Regner, K.R.; Zuk, A.; Van Why, S.K.; Shames, B.D.; Ryan, R.P.; Falck, J.R.; Manthati, V.L.; McMullen, M.E.; Ledbetter, S.R.; Roman, R.J. Protective effect of 20-HETE analogues in experimental renal ischemia reperfusion injury. *Kidney Int.* 2009, 75, 511–517.
 20. Nakamura, T.; Ishii, T.; Miyata, N.; Taniguchi, K.; Tomishima, Y.; Ueki, T.; Sato, M. Design and synthesis of 1-(4-benzoylphenyl) imidazole derivatives as new potent 20-HETE synthase inhibitors. *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* 2004, 14, 5305–5308.
 21. Yanes, L.L.; Lima, R.; Moulana, M.; Romero, D.G.; Yuan, K.; Ryan, M.J.; Baker, R.; Zhang, H.; Fan, F.; Davis, D.D. Postmenopausal hypertension: Role of 20-HETE. *Am. J. Physiol. Regul. Integr. Comp. Physiol.* 2011, 300, 1543–1548.
 22. Chabova, V.C.; Kramer, H.J.; Vaneckova, 762 I.; Vernerova, Z.; Eis, V.; Tesar, V.; Skaroupkova, P.; Thumova, M.; Schejbalova, S.; Huskova, Z. Effects of chronic cytochrome P-450 inhibition on the course of hypertension and end-organ damage in ren-2 transgenic rats. *Vascul. Pharmacol.* 2007, 47, 145–159.
 23. Moreno, J.J. Eicosanoid receptors: Targets for the treatment of disrupted intestinal epithelial homeostasis. *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* 2016, 796, 7–19.
 24. Garcia, V.; Schwartzman, M.L. Recent developments on the vascular effects of 20-hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid. *Curr. Opin. Nephrol. Hypertens.* 2017, 26, 74–82.
 25. Quigley, R.; Baum, M.; Reddy, K.M.; Griener, J.C.; Falck, J.R. Effects of 20-HETE and 19(s)-HETE on rabbit proximal straight tubule volume transport. *Am. J. Physiol. Renal Physiol.* 2000, 278, 949–953.
 26. Omata, K.; Abraham, N.G.; Schwartzman, M.L. Renal cytochrome P-450-arachidonic acid metabolism: Localization and hormonal regulation in shr. *Am. J. Physiol.* 1992, 262, 591–599.
 27. Oliw, E.H. Biosynthesis of 20-hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid (20-HETE) and 12 (s)-HETE by renal cortical microsomes of the cynomolgus monkey. *Eicosanoids* 1990, 3, 161–164.
 28. Lu, M.; Zhu, Y.; Balazy, M.; Reddy, K.M.; Falck, J.R.; Wang, W. Effect of angiotensin ii on the apical K⁺ channel in the thick ascending limb of the rat kidney. *J. Gen. Physiol.* 1996, 108, 537–547.
 29. Escalante, B.; Erlj, D.; Falck, J.R.; McGiff, J.C. Cytochrome P450-dependent arachidonate metabolites affect renal transport in the rabbit. *J. Cardiovasc. Pharmacol.* 1993, 22 Suppl 2, 106–108.
 30. Imig J.D. Epoxides and soluble epoxide hydrolase in cardiovascular physiology. *Physiol. Rev.* 2012, 92, 101–723 130.
 31. Hoopes, S. L., Garcia, V., Edin, M. L., Schwartzman, M. L., & Zeldin, D. C. (2015). Vascular actions of 20-HETE. *Prostaglandins & other lipid mediators*, 120, 9-16.
 32. Chen, L., Tang, S., Zhang, F. F., Garcia, V., Falck, J. R., Laniado Schwartzman, M., ... & Guo, A. M. (2019). CYP4A/20-HETE Regulates Ischemia-induced Neovascularization via Its Actions on Endothelial Progenitor and Preexisting Endothelial Cells. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology*.